

Citizen Participation in the Energy System at the Macro Level

Deliverable WP1-D1

 @EPolities

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About the EnergyPolities Project

EnergyPolities aims to develop an in-depth understanding of citizen participation in the energy transition, the socio-economic and socio-cultural factors which shape it, and the intersections between these and the governance frameworks within which decisions are made. This involves an initial mapping of current patterns of citizen engagement with the energy system, from active consumers to social mobilisation, and from political campaigners to members of community energy projects.

This mapping forms the basis of a typology of citizen participation, which links specific participation forms to the governance structures which condition them and the socio- demographic characteristics of citizens. This typology will subsequently be applied in an in-depth analysis of three case studies of energy projects (two Irish and one mainland EU) that have stimulated significant citizen participation. Integrating both quantitative and qualitative methods, the case studies will reveal linkages between political, institutional and organisational frameworks and citizen participation in the energy system.

EnergyPolities will explore how governance structures intersect with the socio-economic and key socio-cultural factors, including gender, to influence the social acceptability or otherwise of energy infrastructure projects. The business models deployed in each project will be analysed from the perspective of their impact on inclusiveness, gender, democracy and social acceptability; stakeholders' perceptions of distributional and procedural justice will be explored. Recommendations will be developed for how multi-level governance structures, and business models can support inclusive citizen participation and thereby enhance the social acceptability of the energy transition.

For more information see <https://www.ucc.ie/en/energypolities/>

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Executive Summary

This report is a foundational document within WP1 – ‘mapping participation within the energy system’ of the EnergyPolities project. The understandings, descriptions and definitions presented in the report prepare the ground for the realisation of the principal outputs from this package of work.

The aim of this document was to develop an appreciation and understanding of citizen participation and in particular the different modes of participation emerging around energy. Developing this understanding involved addressing civic participation in a general sense, considering public participation in the context of the modern state, and exploring a number of prominent modes of citizen participation, including active consumerism, prosumerism, communitarianism and participatory citizenship.

The concepts of energy justice, energy democracy and energy citizenship were introduced and their importance in understanding citizen participation around energy was outlined. We noted that the concept of the energy citizen remains a contested idea, with some commentators emphasising a normative perspective focused on responsibilities and obligations of ‘good citizens’, while others place a greater prominence on rights, arguing for a more inclusive and participatory conceptualisation.

Following an analysis of modes of participation, the report identified and described six roles that citizen-consumers are permitted to play and/or want to play within the energy system, as shown below.

- the **passive consumer**, the traditional passive receiver of energy;
- the **active consumer**, encouraged to use their purchasing power to influence the market in certain directions;
- the **good citizen**, who just needs to be informed and they will do the ‘right thing’;
- The **constitutionalist**, for whom everything is about understanding and enforcing their legal rights;
- The **producer**, who either individually or collectively with others is involved in the production of energy;
- The **challenger**, who engages in public debate, organises and protests to promote alternative perspectives on energy and the energy system.

1 Introduction

1.1 Context

The EnergyPolitics project aims to develop a deeper understanding of citizen participation in the energy transition, the socio-economic and socio-cultural factors which shape it, and the intersections between these and the governance frameworks within which decisions are made. In this context, the work presented in this report provides an introduction to citizen participation in the energy system. It forms the foundational component of a package of work which aims to map citizen participation around energy, taking a multi-level governance perspective to examine participation at local, regional, national and EU levels.

The first work package of EnergyPolitics aims to identify different forms of participation around energy, develop a systematic typology, and to connect the identified participation forms with the governance and organisational frameworks which condition them. In working to fulfil this aim, the work package has three objectives, as outlined in Box 1 below. This initial deliverable, the product of an in-depth desk study, aims to realise the first of these objectives and establish the foundation from which the other two objectives can be achieved.

1. Understand and classify citizen participation in the energy system as consumers, as citizens and as communitarians;
2. Undertake a comprehensive mapping of existing patterns of participation in the energy system of energy consumers, energy citizens and energy communitarians;
3. Develop a better understanding of how these patterns of energy participation intersect with the organisation and functioning of, and governance in the energy system.

Box 1: Objectives of EnergyPolitics Work Package 1 'Mapping participation in the energy system'

This deliverable, 'Citizen Participation in the Energy System at the Macro Level', therefore focuses on developing an appreciation and understanding of citizen participation and in particular the different modes of participation emerging around energy. It will contrast the top-down emphasis associated with traditional ideas of citizenship engagement with more participatory conceptualisations emerging in discourses on energy democracy and energy citizenship. It will describe key modes of energy-related civic participation and explore the interaction between them. In establishing such an understanding, it prepares the ground for the analysis of emergent governance and organisation frameworks, and the realisation of a typology of citizen participation, which will be presented as deliverables WP1-D2 and WP1-D3 respectively.

1.2 Background

Governments increasingly stress the importance of participation in energy policy as part of a transition to a low-carbon society

(Mullally, Dunphy, & O'Connor, 2018)

How do we operationalise greater civic engagement amongst the general population? With declines in both voter turnout and levels of community volunteerism (Putnam, 1995), this is a question that has informed numerous public debates in recent decades. In response, academic contributions have tried to understand the underlying causes of these very real, though sometimes falsely perceived, inertias in 'civic engagement'. While we can point to examples of this decline in the more obvious forms of civic participation, the reasons for these inertias are complex. Popular narratives often point to citizen apathy¹, however alienation and systemic failures in addressing citizens' concerns have also had a significant role in how they choose to engage (Marsh, O'Toole, & Jones, 2007). A growing disenchantment with formal electoral politics, for varying reasons, has resulted in what some commentators see as a breakdown in effective public consultation (Kim & Ball-Rokeach, 2006; Pahad, 2005).

David Booher (2008) suggests that over the past four decades attempts at promoting public participation have more often than not been co-opted by official actors into managerial strategies for regularising conflicts. According to Healey (2008), this emphasis on participation as a procedural requirement has resulted in effectively squeezing out any transformative energy that may be present in a collective action or social movement. Consequently, how engagements are organised, and by whom, have very real impacts on their potential for improving public services and policy making. Having said that, Booher (2008) and others acknowledge that adopting more citizen-centric approaches to public governance and policy making can offer significant transformative potential, particularly a bottom-up renewal of the democratic process.

It can be argued Sherry Arnstein's (1969) seminal paper *The Ladder of Citizen Participation* helped kick off this new wave of interest in the structural dimensions to how citizens engage with the public governance and policy making domains of the state. Arnstein's eight-rung ladder, see Figure 1 below, identifies three key areas of citizen participation which are characterised as: (i) degrees of citizen power; (ii) degrees of tokenism; and (iii) activities defined essentially as 'nonparticipation'. The favoured activities of those taking a top-down approach (*i.e.* consultation and informing) are rightly categorised as tokenistic, a sentiment reflected in the trenchant cynicism of citizens experiencing

¹ Albeit in such narratives, citizens are often reduced to 'voters', and the discourse typically centred around what such participation (or lack of participation) would mean for electoral politics.

these types of participation. Arnstein illustrates this point with her reproduction of a 1968 French student protest poster, see also Figure 1 below, which “encapsulates participation without redistribution of power [as] an empty and frustrating process for the powerless” (Arnstein, 1969).

Figure 1 Arnstein's Ladder of citizen participation. The higher up the ladder the greater the level of participation. Also, a reproduction of the 1968 student poster, illustrates tokenistic approaches such as consultation are readily acknowledged as such, translation: "I participate, you participate, he participates, we participate, you all participate...they profit".

Of particular importance for Arnstein, and which is reflected in her ladder, is the acknowledgement of the (re)negotiation of power that lies at the heart of all citizen participation activities. While this framing was specifically applied to critically assess planning processes and the socio-spatial dimensions of power in top-down technocratic systems, it also suggests that all participation is very much delineated by the assigning and relinquishing of power. This perspective can very easily be applied to citizens engaging with the energy system, who remain largely absent from any real decision-making. While being absent from decision-making is not necessarily, in and of itself, indicative of a lack of human agency – one may choose not to participate after all – it does require further examination. This becomes more apparent when we accept that the underlying systemic factors preventing participation often mask other hidden reasons for such absences, and do not simply reflect a certain laziness or apathy on the part of the citizen.

Arnstein's Ladder has received numerous critiques over the years, from its perceived limitations in providing insights (Collins & Ison, 2006), to the ladder analogy being better served as 'scaffolding' to account for the structural variations – while still acknowledging its hierarchical nature – of power in say the health sector (Tritter & McCallum, 2006), or the inclusive community development initiatives working with Ireland's Traveller and Gypsy communities (Ryder, 2014). More recently, Cardullo and Kitchin (2019) apply Arnstein's Ladder to examine citizen participation in place making and city governance under the guise of the 'smart citizen'. They note that since Arnstein first presented her ladder, there has been a significant shift on the part of states in entrenching a variety of neoliberalisms into their national and local political economies. This shift has been shaped by a confluence of political ideologies, state policies, institutional cultures, market practices and legal frameworks. With regards to the procurement, distribution and consumption of energy – as with other facets of the state – very often, the only form of acceptable participation remains that of 'the consumer' with choice being defined in terms of affordability and the types of services one can acquire from a defined marketplace of providers.

Consumerism, therefore, has tended to characterise most so-called 'citizen-centric' approaches taken within the energy system, which under Arnstein is best understood as situated somewhere between 'non-participation' and 'tokenism'. Unpacking how citizens are framed within the smart city (Cardullo & Kitchin, 2019) and indeed the energy transition (Lennon et al., 2020) is critical if we are to understand whether 'citizen-centric' initiatives really do offer an alternative to, or are a reinforcement of, the current neoliberal status quo. Therefore, we must examine in more detail what exactly constitutes citizen participation and what it means within the context of the energy transition.

1.3 Structure of the document

The report is divided into four sections as outlined below:

- 1 – Introduction, presents an overview of the report, details the background to the work, provides context for the task undertaken, describes the research aims and objectives and presents the structure of the document.
- 2 – Methodology, considers the philosophical and theoretical background to the research, and details the research methods and techniques employed.
- 3 – Civic participation, forwards an overview of different modes of civic participation. It explores key concepts, theories and concepts central to energy participation including: energy justice, energy democracy, and energy citizenship. Finally it discusses a number of prominent existing and emerging mode of citizen energy participation.

- 4 – Summary and conclusions, presents a summation of the findings, and highlights the relevance of the report to the related work on developing a typology and analysing relevant emergent governance and organisation frameworks.

2 Methodology

2.1 Research approach

This report is based upon desk research *i.e.*, the collection and analysis of data from existing resources. Specifically this entailed a review of relevant literature from both academic and so-called grey literature². Literature reviews are a critical part of the research process, as a means of exploring existing knowledge, theories and practices in the relevant areas (Webster & Watson, 2002) *i.e.*, setting the scene for the research to be conducted. However, such a review is not just a preliminary task to be enduring and quickly got out of the way before the start of ‘real’ research (Onwuegbuzie & Freis, 2016) – rather it stands in its own right as a research method which can produce new knowledge and deliver new insights, for example through what Torraco (2005) refers to as an integrative literature review. The following section outlines the methods used in this desk study.

2.2 Methods

Fink’s (2010, p. 5) seven tasks³ in reviewing literature is a useful framing mechanism to describe the methods used in this report.

1. A selection of a research question orientates the literature review. In this study, the over-arching research question is concerned with the ways in which citizens participate, how they wish to participate, and/or are allowed to participate in the energy system. Accordingly, this report reviews literature that pertains to that question
2. The second task relates to the selection of sources of literature. The principal sources of literature used for this research were the UCC library catalogue, and bibliographic databases which were either freely accessible or made available through university subscriptions. Cognisant that database services have different strengths, a number were utilised to overcome the weaknesses that may be associated with individual services. The primary commercial databases utilised were: Science Direct, SCOPUS, and JSTOR, with Google Scholar used as a supplementary source.

² Research published outside of the traditional commercial or academic channels – including for example, reports, working papers, government documents, white papers and evaluations.

³ (i) selecting research question; (ii) selecting sources of literature; (iii) choosing search terms & combinations; (iv) applying practical screening criteria; (v) applying methodical screening criteria; (vi) ‘doing’ the review; and (vii) synthesising the results.

3. The databases outlined above were queried using Boolean keyword searches, where combinations of words and phrases using Boolean operators 'and', 'or', 'not' to search for relevant material. Such searches are flexible and allow for sophisticated searches⁴. In addition to such searches described above, relevant literature which may have been missed were found through what might be termed a snowballing strategy⁵.
4. The next couple of steps involve applying screening criteria to reduce the amount of identified literature, increasing the efficiency and relevance of the review. Firstly, practical screening criteria are applied to *"identify a broad range of articles that may be potentially usable in that they cover the topic of interest, are in a language you can read, and are in a publication you respect and can be obtained in a timely manner"* (Fink, 2010, p. 59).
5. Following application of this practical screening, methodical screening criteria was applied to the residual documents, focusing on: methodological background; apparent quality and rigour of the work; *etc.* The outcome of this iterative screening process was a collection of the literature which was small enough to review and comprehensive enough that there were no glaring omissions.
6. Next was the actual review of the selected and collected literature, comprising an iterative process of search – read – annotate – organise – summarise – analyse. The use of reference management software during this task facilitated more efficient reading, notetaking and organisation of documents.
7. The final step is synthesising the results. The objective of which should not be to demonstrate the number of citations which were included but rather to produce something of value, a 'good review will be more than descriptive. It will be original, perceptive and analytical' (Jesson & Lacey, 2006, p. 142).

The steps in conducting a literature review are of course carried out in an iterative fashion.

3 Civic participation

3.1 Understanding modes of citizen participation

Before the emergence of a broader understanding of the concept of governance, conventional political science scholarship traditionally relied on rather narrow interpretations and definitions for

⁴ Examples of some initial search term combinations employed include: 'citizen' OR 'consumer' AND 'energy' AND 'participation' AND; 'active consumer' AND 'energy'; 'energy' AND 'community'; 'energy' AND 'citizenship' OR 'democracy'.

⁵ This included: 'backward snowballing', literature listed in bibliographies of papers identified through keyword searches; 'forward snowballing', literature that has cited the identified papers; and relationship 'snowballing', articles recommended by the bibliographic databases based on relevance scoring.

understanding politics, policy making, and the state (Waylen, Celis, Kantola, & Weldon, 2013). In recent years, this has changed with governance studies opening up to considering a more diverse range of actors and activities, allowing for a re-evaluation of the multifaceted nature of polities. This has also led to changes in conceptualising and perceiving the state. For example, in a recent State Violence Research Network podcast (SVRN, 2020), Keagan Day discussed his 2020 ANZSOC conference paper on understanding the state as *existing as a verb*. In the very act of doing statecraft, the state shapes – and is indeed shaped by – conflictual relationships to power that require constant enactment and reification to ensure its own survival (Day, 2020). This theme of highly focused, reactive exchanges between the state and its critics (in Day’s example, state and non-state actor violence) is equally important when we look at citizen participation more generally.

As Erik Mostert (2003) suggests, effective public participation is not simply an accessory to aiding the management of say strategic public utilities (in his example, water), but is in fact an entirely different mode of governance. The range and form of political participation in democratic societies has also expanded to encompass a diverging spectrum of activities including voting, demonstrating, volunteering, boycotting, blogging, and flash mobs, with protest having a particular resonance for citizens across the globe (Theocharis & Van Deth, 2018). Taking many forms, from physical (sometimes violent) confrontations between citizens and police to online hashtag campaigns on social media platforms, the breadth and scope for individualised self-expression has widened considerably. This expansion also reflects a widening dissatisfaction amongst citizens who feel disenfranchised from contemporary political processes and correlates with a general decline in political trust. Political trust, in this context, stems from citizens evaluating government and/or institutional performances in accordance with the normative expectations of the general public (Miller & Listhaug, 1990).

The concept of political trust will receive further attention later in the report, but before we do it is important to understand what we mean when we refer to citizen participation. Using Baum’s (2001) interpretation, citizen participation in its simplest form describes the involvement of citizens in public decision-making processes. Deconstructing the term, and depending on your application of it, a ‘citizen’ can be either an individual or an organised group, while ‘participation’ can encompass practices ranging from observation to the utilisation and application of social and economic power. The term itself has come into common parlance to describe the remedial efforts of governments to engage with what were once termed ‘inactive citizens’ in specific key infrastructural projects. It has now expanded to encapsulate a number of citizen-oriented activities led by the state, ranging from community development projects to national social planning and other social action initiatives.

Proponents usually emphasise the potential for empowering usually-disenfranchised individuals and communities, by fostering greater levels of knowledge and problem-solving skills in those groups being targeted. Consequently, citizen participation can include anything from information sharing and deepening relationships between the state and its citizens, to building greater community resilience and strengthening local capacity for maintaining or instigating change (Baum, 2001). When we refer to participation we must also consider such activities in terms of ‘representation’, given certain citizens – especially those with economic and social privilege – already have the established socio-economic networks that support their efforts to participate in political actions or instigate change that reflects their interests. Those with less socio-economic privilege invariably do not have these networks without some concerted effort on the part of government. How this is done can take on a number of forms, from government engagements with loosely aligned community groups and formal organisations, to citizen fora, meetings, inquiries, action planning, and/or technical assistance.

Theocharis & Van Deth (2018) have classified these various approaches into a multi-dimensional taxonomy that encompasses voting, digitally networked participation, institutionalised participation, protest, civic participation, and consumerist participation. They also argue that the antecedents of consumerist, civic, and digitally networked participation resemble older modes of engagement such as protest and institutionalised participation, which they do. While contributing to a wider inventory of political participation, the authors also acknowledge their departure as new and distinct modes of political participation. This is set to increase as digital technologies become more integrated into political systems in order to accommodate younger citizens who tend to favour them (Bang, 2009). The consequences, however, for engaged citizenship remains unclear given the extent and speed of exponential change associated with these technologies.

The inherent difficulties associated with operationalising citizen participation have long been acknowledged (*e.g.* see E. M. Burke, 1968), with tensions between participatory democracy and professional expertise a significant factor. This has often led to confusion in both the use and the application of language and terminology as citizens and professionals negotiate how to work together on specific projects. Therefore, how terms are used and understood by different stakeholders is important. Without clear communication that provides a common understanding between various groups of stakeholder, the use and application of language and specific terminologies can turn out to be counterproductive even when stakeholders share common goals and desired outcomes.

3.1.1 ACTIVE CONSUMERISM

Consumerism has long been recognised as a contributing factor to much of the current environmental and energy related issues we face. So much so that it can be considered a fundamental causal factor,

while also underlining many of the social injustices citizens face in relation to energy extraction and production (Erickson, 1997). Its significance can be understood by the depth and breadth of attention it receives from key thinkers on these topics; from academics, intellectuals and religious spokespersons to social and political commentators across all media (Campbell, 2010). Thorstein Veblen's (1899) book, 'The Theory of the Leisure Class', is an early example of writing on the then growing phenomenon of 'leisure time' for certain social classes, and the changing economic and social structures facilitating this newer form of capitalism. Though consumer culture, in the modern sense, began to emerge much earlier (during the seventeenth century with the expansion of European imperialism and the proliferation of new saleable commodities from newly acquired colonies) it was the shift away from utilitarian functionality to displays of conspicuous levels of consumption and waste to denote status which were of particular interest to Veblen and others. As industrial output ramped up over the course of the twentieth century, social narratives espousing what is to be considered the 'good life' became more intrinsically linked to consumption and consumerist practices cutting through established religious, ethnic and class differences (James & Szeman, 2010), culminating in for example, the so-called American Dream espoused during the 1950s.

Indeed, consumerism has often been portrayed as a uniquely American form of materialism, especially by numerous American industrialists and certain European intellectuals. This was not always presented in the most positive terms with American materialism often portrayed more as a beacon of mediocrity (Stearns, 2001), where instant gratification is manufactured through the construct of artificial needs and wants, than as an expression of its more high-minded ideals such as freedom of expression or 'the pursuit of happiness'. Essentially, consumerism (*i.e.* economic materialism) can be characterised as citizens (in their role as consumers) participating in the market in so far as they are allowed to 'rationally' choose one product/service over another. This general passivity, however, is occasionally interspersed by episodes of 'consumer mania' or 'fever' for certain products codified as highly desirable. Exemplars of this could include the scramble for tulips in seventeenth century Netherlands (Bianchi, 1998) or whatever the latest must-have Christmas toy happens to be each year.

The proceeding economic and environmental shocks that occurred since the high watermark of the 1950s has led to a certain degree of re-evaluation of consumerist principles in popular discourse with many of these being verbalised in terms of their passivity and activity. The passive consumer, for example, consumes media content, services, manufactured goods, and food products without considering how that product was made or the social and environmental costs associated with their production. Throughout the 1980s the social sciences increasingly challenged this formerly dominant presentation of mass consumption, reconceptualising its associated practices as either being 'passive' or 'active' depending on the motivations and behaviours of those consumers involved. In terms of

energy, this been particularly noticeable with the role out of smart technologies and participatory, user-orientated co-design approaches positioning consumers in more proactive roles as both active innovators and co-producers of energy (Fox, Foulds, & Robison, 2017). However, like passive consumerism, the 'active consumer' is equally very much a construct that is defined and legitimised within the rather narrow bands of reference put forward by incumbent energy actors, many of whom remain intent on maintaining the status quo. For Yolande Strengers (2013) the active consumer operates within a 'smart utopia' that resonates with the technological utopian ideals of the past. Deconstructing the notion of the 'smart' consumer, whom she refers to as *Resource Man*, she notes the obvious gender dimensions the term occupies whereby a 'new' energy consumer is imagined in a highly functional and masculine ways with the consumer, in this incarnation, presented as technologically informed, efficient and above all rational (*ibid.*). This construct sits well with many actors in the (still) male-dominated industries of engineering and computer science, and supported by the field of economics, who have tended to champion it.

3.1.2 PROSUMERISM

Having emerged from the many cooperative self-help movements of the twentieth century, the idea of converging consumption and production gained increasing traction after the term 'prosumer' was coined in the book 'The Third Wave' (Toffler, 1980). Toffler used the term to describe new ICT technology users who were producing content using commons-based peer production (CBPP). Usually, this type of activity would see large numbers of people working together cooperatively over the internet, using crowdsourcing to address a specific topic or problem. According to Benkler (2016) the key characteristics of CBPP include:

1. a decentralised approach taken to identifying problems and developing solutions;
2. the exploitation of diverse motivations towards a common goal;

while at the same time,

3. decoupling governance and management structures from traditional property and contract considerations.

Underlying this is the distinction between production for use and production for exchange. When people produce for use, production and consumption are united in the same person. When they produce for exchange, then production and consumption are separated.

(Kotler, 2010)

For Toffler and others, a prosumer therefore is someone who is able to produce at least some of the goods and services for their own consumption, while a consumer will put their time into producing one thing and use their earnings to purchase all the other things that they need or desire. As Toffler saw it, there have been three waves of human history with the Industrial Age (*i.e.* the second wave) resulting a decoupling of production and consumption that characterised the agricultural economies that preceded it. People who up until then could be considered prosumers, *i.e.* growing their own food and selling on any surpluses they might have, were forced to switch to much more delineated economic activities whereby the site of production (the factory or workshop where they engaged in highly-specialised labour) became separated from their main spheres of consumption (the food and trade goods used in the home, and other products now considered to be consumer goods and services). This paradigm shift has been disrupted again as society moves to post-industrial configurations dominated by ICT and the prosumer-orientated economic models that favour these technologies. Philip Kotler (2010) brings together Toffler’s ideas in the following table:

Table 1 Toffler's thesis on prosumers and consumers (source: Kotler, 2010)

	Thesis First Wave	Antithesis Second Wave	Synthesis Third Wave
Dominant Institution (mix of prosumers and consumers)	Agriculture Many prosumers (Sector A is large) Few consumers (Sector B is small)	Industry (factory) Few prosumers (Sector A is small) Many consumers (Sector B is large)	Home More prosumers (Sector A gets larger) Fewer consumers (Sector B gets smaller)
Dominant processes	Self-production	Industrialisation Marketisation	De-industrialisation De-marketisation De-massification
Norm	Survival	Efficiency (as producers) Indulgence (as consumers)	Individuation
Social nexus	Kinship and friendship; tribe	Contracts and transactions; workplace	Family and friends; neighbourhood

According to Toffler the majority of people fall into one of two sectors, either Sector A comprising prosumers (the dominant group in the first – agricultural – wave) or Sector B comprising consumers (the dominant group of the second – industrial – wave). As the numbers for both Sector A and Sector B shift, Toffler sees this as evidence that we are entering a third wave whose social nexus is situated in the neighbourhood and the home with family and friends instead of ‘the workplace’. The prosumer is now becoming more entrenched in the energy system with a rising number of small and medium enterprises generating and consuming their own energy. Parag and Sovacool (2016), use the examples of smart devices, new battery technology, solar photovoltaic panels and vehicle-to-grid electric

vehicles to indicate the transformative potential prosumption can have for energy practices. Though they do warn that the electricity sector will need to undergo significant changes in order to accommodate this transformation.

Also, prosumer capitalism is not without its darker aspects with critics (*e.g.*, Chen, 2015) pointing to its contribution to a deepening immiseration of workers and increases in workload due to understaffing as prosumers do many of the same tasks for free; to amplifying pre-existing social stratifications with the 'haves' able to afford to opt out of prosuming while the 'have nots' have no choice but to. All of which is leading to increased alienation for those (*e.g.* the elderly, the disabled, those with less economic and social privilege) who either may not be able to afford the new technologies needed to prosume, find them difficult to master or chose not to engage with them for some other reason (Ritzer, 2015). Individuation is clearly not without its shortcomings.

3.1.3 COMMUNITARIANISM

While the term communitarianism originated out of the British Chartist movement of the mid-1800s, in response to socialist thinking at the time that espoused communal living, it wasn't until the early 1980s before the term was more systematically developed and expanded largely in response to the writings of John Rawls⁶ (Tam, 2019). A core tenet has been that the normative emphasis on individualism and the precepts of liberal theory that have characterised much of twentieth century market capitalism has resulted in deep systemic incoherencies within liberalism, especially in terms of distributional and procedural justice. Liberalism's most popular current incarnation, neoliberalism, for example has only deepened these inherent contradictions. For example, while presenting a self-imagined characterisation of being 'post-racial' neoliberalism's many proponents show a deep antipathy towards democratic politics. Instead, we have seen a championing of political and financial hegemonies that further entrench socio-economic insecurities that have tended to promote far-right reactions as an alternative form of racialised moral economy (Saull, 2018).

Communitarian philosophers (MacIntyre, 1981, 1988; Sandel, 1982; Taylor, 1989; Walzer, 1983) have instead sought to focus on the role community plays in shaping the actions and behaviours of individuals, while emphasising that by idealising the role of 'the individual' liberal theorists have failed to acknowledge the significant importance community has in shaping society. Therefore, in order to establish a 'good society' the communitarian contention is that there needs to be a balance between

⁶ John Rawls' (1971) book *A Theory of Justice* received considerable attention from communitarian philosophers over the proceeding decades who very much objected to its portrayal of human beings as somehow locked into a liberal construct of atomistic individuals behaving independently and responding rationally to economic and social externalities, while ignoring the social embeddedness to which we all adhere (Bell, 1993).

several popular, though at times conflicting, normative principles most notably ideas on individual autonomy and notions of the common good (Etzioni, 2018). These interpretations of morality and autonomy lie at the heart of communitarian thinking, whether it is from ‘communitarian liberals’ like Amitai Etzioni or ecological communitarians like J. Baird Callicott (1989), and are marked by a strong tension between the two. Also, it gives rise to a fundamental question for each case: *“to what extent should individuals be taught, exhorted, seduced or induced to behave in conformity with the needs of economic, social or ecological rationalization”* (Bowring, 1997, p. 94). This question is critical given a basic assumption of communitarianism is that a strong community must be compatible with the moral authenticity of the people comprising it. Consequently, for communitarianism in all its incarnations, it is important that members of a given community are able to recognise and take ownership of their social conduct and its results because of their ability to practice free will. One arena where we can explore this further is around popular discourses around energy.

In a recent paper on participative environmental policy integration (EPI) in the Irish energy sector, Mullally *et al.* (2018) identify communitarianism as one of six differing narratives coalescing around current social representations of the energy system and the transition to a low-carbon economy. These, they suggest are essentially ‘discourse coalitions’, using Maarten Hajer’s (1993) definition they comprise an ‘ensemble of a set of story lines, the actors that utter these story lines and the practices that conform to these story lines, [are] all organised around a discourse’. The six discourse coalitions they identify include: 1.) paternalist, 2.) majoritarian, 3.) consumerist, 4.) constitutionalist, 5.) communitarian, and 6.) deliberative. A characterisation of the communitarian discourse coalition is outline in Table 2 below.

Table 2: A breakdown of communitarian discourse coalitions in terms of their narrative and institutional implications (adapted from: Mullally et al., 2018)

Discourse Coalitions	Actor Constellation	Narrative	Energy Citizenship Framing	Implications for policy integration
Communitarian	Political parties Individuals	Citizenship anchored in community membership	Citizens as communities. Citizens / communities entitled to involvement in, and benefit from, energy projects. Citizens / communities as prosumers.	Decentralised, bottom-up communication

For communitarians, citizenship (including the increasingly popular though contested ‘energy citizenship’) is defined by in relation to community. For example, market-orientated financial packages designed to promote renewable energy have not proved to be an incentive for communities given the

capital costs involved. Therefore, those paying in terms of impact (e.g. communities in and where wind farms are erected) rarely benefit from those projects. As one contributor in Mullally *et al.* (2018) puts it “nothing empowers citizens more than being part owner of energy supply and delivery”. Another notable finding from the authors indicates that ‘the prosumer’ is very often portrayed as a collective rather than individual construct. This enmeshment of the prosumer and the communitarian may prove problematic as the shift to low-carbon energy configurations deepens.

3.1.4 PARTICIPATORY CITIZENSHIP

In reality ‘democracy’ is related to a whole variety of ideas and it has a range of meanings. These might involve, variously, accessibility, popularity, and inclusion as well as openness, transparency, responsiveness, civility, and other values.

(Mackie, 2009)

Citizen participation is an integral component of democracy, with many commentators pointing to the positive effects participation has on the body politic, particularly in terms of trust. Changes in levels of participation can act as an indicator of the overall quality, robustness and general good health of the democratic traditions of the state, and is seen as vital to democratic citizenship and the process of democratic decision-making. For example, citizens actively engaging with their social networks enable them to express their specific interests and expectation of governments, consequently magnifying individual voices through inclusive channels. Zhang (2015) has framed this in terms of perceived procedural fairness and/or perceived disagreement with group decision making outcomes, as well as individual intentions for future participation. In an earlier paper, Michels and de Graaf (2010) charted the growing influence of citizens in Western European countries in impacting policy making by examining the probability of these claims in their analysis of two local participatory policymaking projects in the Netherlands. From this work, they were able to outline the various aspects to citizen participation in the democratic process, see Table 3 below, presenting them in terms of the types of engagement involved and the theoretical perspectives that underpin each approach.

Table 3 Aspects of citizen participation and democracy: a framework for analysis (source: Michels & de Graaf, 2010)

Aspects	Clarification	Theoretical perspective
Inclusion	Allows for individual voices to be heard (openness, diversity of opinions <i>etc.</i>)	Social capital Deliberative democracy
Civic skills and virtues	Improved civic skills (debating public issues, running meetings) and civic virtues (public engagement and responsibility, feeling a public citizen, active participation in public life, reciprocity)	Participatory democracy Social capital

Deliberation	Rational decisions based on public reasoning (exchange of arguments and shifts of preferences)	Deliberative democracy
Legitimacy	Support for process and outcome	Participatory democracy

While a general understanding of the term 'participation' can be found in the literature, particularly amongst democratic theory scholars, its meaning in both popular and policy discourses often remains somewhat vague or even contradictory. This has led to the rather mixed outcomes that we have seen for the energy transition to date. While citizens express strong support for using renewable energy sources, to meet the challenges of human-induced climate change, this support has not translated so seamlessly when considering local contexts. The reasons for this are complicated and language plays a significant part in the normalisation of citizen expectations to evolving social orders such as those contributing to the energy transition. How those in authority use language to communicate complex ideas to citizens can become a significant causal factor when trying to mobilise largescale public actions. However, when the message is misapplied or communicated incoherently, it can lead to unintended negative reactions from the public to what on the surface appear to be shared common goals. Taken in this context:

participation refers to actions demonstrating forms of involvement performed by parties within evolving structures of talk

(Goodwin & Goodwin, 2004, p. 222)

In order to coordinate any action with their fellow participants, there is often a clear need on the part of people to demonstrate to one another what they are doing and how they communicate their alignment to commonly agreed objectives. What Goodwin and Goodwin (2004) refer to as the 'interactive work' that speakers and listeners engage in. This process sees speakers respond to listeners as active co-participants, systematically modifying what they are saying to take into account the response(s) of the listener. As such, language and embodied action are crucial components of this social ordering. This is as true for familial environments as it is for participants in largescale, multi-tiered networks such as the state.

3.2 Energy participation – key concepts

Participation in the energy system is increasingly to the fore in the discourse on the ongoing energy transition. The acknowledgement of a need for greater civic participation is a response to the growing acceptance that society's decisions around energy need to be fairer⁷. This discourse has also resulted

⁷ Including but not limited to the growing discourse around the need for a 'just transition' (Heffron & McCauley, 2018).

in increased discussion of concepts such as energy democracy, a conceptualisation of a more inclusive, fairer, more democratic energy system, and of energy citizenship, an exploration of the role that citizens could (or perhaps should) be allowed to play in a more participatory energy system.

3.2.1 ENERGY JUSTICE

Feelings of unfairness are often key to understanding disputes over changes to the energy system generally, and on energy projects specifically. In relation to energy, justice can be conceptualised as involving three dimensions: distributional (ensuring the costs and benefits of energy systems are distributed according to principles of equity and fairness); procedural (ensuring decision-making procedures in relation to energy projects are fair, transparent, informative and inclusive); and recognitive (ensuring different social groups do not feel marginalised or ignored as a result of decisions).

Distributional justice: Social justice and fairness are core values by which many citizens assess energy technologies and initiatives. There are concerns that the financial and environmental costs of energy systems disproportionately affect those who are vulnerable or disadvantaged in other ways, such as the energy poor. Poorer or less-educated citizens may be left behind in a future which requires a higher standard of energy literacy.

Procedural justice: Gross (2007) shows that procedural justice plays a fundamental role in the prediction of attitudes towards new energy projects. According to Tyler (2000, p. 121), judgments on the fairness of procedures are mainly influenced by the existence of ‘opportunities for participation, the neutrality of the forum, the trustworthiness of the authorities, and the degree to which people receive treatment with dignity and respect’.

Recognitive justice: Opposition to energy projects is often motivated by intangible factors such as a perception that they will lead to the erosion of a place’s identity, or the feeling of an individual or group that their voices have not been ‘heard’ in the decision-making process. Consequently, it is important that consultative or deliberate processes make room for all perspectives, and that concerns about the impact of projects on local landscapes and identity are recognised and taken into account⁸.

3.2.2 ENERGY DEMOCRACY

Burke and Stephens (2018, p. 79) suggest that energy democracy is ‘a part of the process of ongoing struggles for economic and political democratization as expressed through the practical project of

⁸ John Barry’s green republican account of a just transition strategy highlights the importance of participation for the energy transition as neatly encapsulated by his argument that there should be ‘no carbon taxation without participation and agitation’ (2019, p. 3)

energy transitions'. The energy domain (both in policy and practice terms) is increasingly to the fore in public discourse and of interest to the general public, not least due to a growing acknowledgement for the need to radically change our energy system to meet the challenge of climate change. What was once a techno-centric policy domain is increasingly hearing calls for more public participation and a greater democratic voice in energy decision-making (Healy & Barry, 2017).

There is a growing realisation that the ongoing energy transition is more than just the substitution of one set of energy sources for another or the adoption of new technologies⁹. Decarbonising society will inherently both require and result in major societal transformation, this will need not just public acceptance of decisions but also public acceptability within the decision-making process *i.e.*, what might be described as fairness. For example, Lennon *et al.* (2019, p. 3) argue that 'strengthening democratic legitimacy can help promote greater levels of social acceptability' of renewable energy projects. This social legitimacy¹⁰ is key to realising the transformation embodied in the decarbonisation goals of the energy transition.

Szulecki (2018) identifies a number of elements of energy democracy found in the literature, namely: increased participation in the decision-making; increased public and community ownership of production; increased societal benefits such as: employment, sufficiency, quality of life, sustainability. He forwards a view that energy democracy can be thought of as "an ideal political goal, in which the citizens are the recipients, stakeholders (as consumers/producers) and account holders of the entire energy sector policy" (*Ibid.* 2018, p. 35).

3.2.3 ENERGY CITIZENSHIP

Energy citizenship is a concept which has gained significant currency in policy debates, though its meaning remains quite nebulous. In the broadest terms, it means '*the public are conceived as active rather than passive stakeholders in energy system evolution and...the potential for action is framed by notions of equitable rights and responsibilities across society for dealing with the consequences of energy consumption, notably climate change*' (Devine-Wright, 2007, p. 71). Mullally *et al.* (2018) see citizenship within the energy domain as comprising rights and responsibilities – founded on key sustainability principles, including participation, equity, and justice – which are facilitated by processes

⁹ Of course technological fixes are attractive to both incumbent businesses and many policy-makers, for as Heberlein (2012, p. 3) observes in relation to such solutions: '*they require that people do basically nothing. We simply change the environment and go on living much as we have in the past. Problem solved*'

¹⁰ We prefer use of the term 'social legitimacy' over 'social licence', although the terms are sometimes used interchangeably. Social licence is a techno-centric term which infers a discrete preliminary operation, that results in a pseudo-legalistic entitlement. We would argue that this is contrary to the essence of energy justice. In contrast, we see social legitimacy as an integral and ongoing component of the activity (such as policy process, energy project, *etc.*).

that enable collaborative responses to challenges. However they note the continued contestation of the concept and suggest the key question remains ‘*what kind of citizens are participants invited to be?*’ (Ibid. 2018, p. 75).

In contrast to the perspective combination of rights and responsibilities, energy citizenship is often – and quite problematically – conceptualised with an emphasis on responsibility, which tends to be privatised and placed on individuals in their role as consumers. This focus on personal responsibility disregards the substantial influence social contexts and socio-technical systems have on energy-related practices (Dunphy, Revez, Gaffney, Lennon, Ramis Aguilo, et al., 2017). Such a restrictive consumerist perspective would serve to significantly limit the scope of citizen participation around energy to primarily consumer-based rights and market-based influence (Mullally et al., 2018), in what Scerri and Magee (2012, p. 392) describe as exercising ‘consumer sovereignty through a privatized ethics of rational choice’.

Acknowledging that the scale and nature of citizen participation in the future energy system remains an open question, Dunphy *et al.* (2018, p. 31) argue that a successful decarbonisation requires citizens to embrace the transition as something of which they are a part, rather than an external imposition, and that this in turn requires ‘modes of governance which are inclusive and participatory, and which allow all citizens to become full stakeholders in the transition and share in its benefits’.

3.3 Modes of energy participation

3.3.1 THE PASSIVE CONSUMER – CONSUMPTION- BASED ROLE

The traditional view of the citizen in the energy domain – if they were considered at all – is as a ‘fortunate recipient’ of a key component of modern comfort and living, from a benevolent, ‘technical marvel’ of an energy industry. This transactional relationship involved the energy industry selling a commodity¹¹ (albeit portrayed as a wondrous one), to passive consumers, in return for payment. In this perspective, a citizen’s only permitted role in the energy system was as a customer. The techno-centric energy industry were the accepted experts and their views greatly influenced, if not actively directed energy policy in many countries.

However, in recent decades there has been a growing (if sometimes reluctant, and at times lukewarm) acceptance of new roles for citizens in the energy sphere. The following sections outline prominent examples of existing and emerging alternative modes of participation.

¹¹ Traditionally many of the companies involved in supplying energy, particularly but not only that supplied through centralised grids were state owned and/or highly regulated, highlighting that energy while a commodity was also considered a strategic resource at a national level.

3.3.2 THE ACTIVE CONSUMER – MARKET-BASED ROLE

The conception of the active consumer revolves on the notion of citizens supposedly having untapped market influence through their purchasing power as consumers. This market-based representation sees the citizen as a so-called ‘active’ consumer – empowered by existing transactional rights and responsibilities – being able to instigate (and/or support) systemic change by multiple individual consumers making ‘smart choices’ and thereby influencing the market. The emphasis here is on the individual contributing to a potential collective action, resulting in market signals being received by energy companies¹². Critics would contend that it ignores the limited (and indeed limiting) nature of choices the ‘active’ consumer actually has been given with regard to energy. Choice for the citizen, framed as a consumer, is largely defined by her selection of one product or service over another. She very rarely is allowed to play an active role in the planning and development of the product or service, never mind in the systemic structures that deliver that product or service to her. Although labelled ‘active’ in a conscious contrast with the traditional passive role envisaged for the consumer, other than the purchasing decisions (which in most cases will involve selection from a rather limited range of options) – the ‘active consumer’ is still quite passive in their engagement with the energy system.

3.3.3 THE GOOD CITIZEN – INFORMATION-BASED ROLE

The need to respond to the climate crisis has been accompanied by the conception of the ‘good citizen’ *i.e.*, citizen-consumers who just need to be informed and educated, and they will do the ‘right thing’¹³ (Lennon et al., 2020). This rather paternalistic, representation of the citizen is based on an information-deficit model, whereby the citizen-consumer is simply considered ill-formed and therefore needs to be educated and persuaded to use a favoured energy technology ‘correctly’ or ‘more efficiently’. This form of civic participation follows the information-based model with government and industry elites continuing to direct and control change from the top-down. It is favoured particularly by those interested in minimum disruption to existing energy configurations. It puts responsibility squarely on the individual to instigate change, through self-education, rather than acknowledging the requisite systemic challenges that individual citizens are largely incapable of addressing. In doing so, it arguably represents a transfer of responsibilities for change from those with power and resources (*i.e.*, energy companies and governmental bodies) to individual citizen-consumers, who have neither. This is deeply problematic as it ignores the many intersectional experiences of citizens who are expected to deliver on what is a highly-centralised, limited (and

¹² Collective purchasing through both formal co-operatives and informal collectives significantly increases an individual’s market-power, but does not substantially alter the scope of the role consumers play in the energy system

¹³ In whatever terms this has been defined by those in power.

limiting) form of participation. Furthermore, although this conception transfers many of the (moral) responsibilities for realising the energy transition to citizen-consumers – it is not accompanied by a change in the ‘rules of engagement’. Citizen-consumer participation remains structured by the legally-mandated processes set down by those very same elites who are incentivised to maintain the existing status quo – participation squarely defined in terms of commodity-orientated, transactional engagements. While this is the case, it is also true that some citizens are not adverse to this kind of arrangement with the responsibility for planning and delivering energy being delegated to someone else. While not illegitimate, it is by no means deliberative.

3.3.4 THE CONSTITUTIONALIST – RIGHTS-BASED PARTICIPATION

Mullally *et al.* (2018) identify another form of citizen participation, the main protagonist for whom is represented in the form of a ‘constitutionalist’ who mostly sees participation through their concern for legalistic definitions of rights and how the law is to be interpreted within the context of accommodating change. Again, much the like market-based and information-based approaches the emphasis here is on maintaining pre-existing socio-technical structures by instigating non-disruptive changes to existing legal arrangements. This form of citizen participation has also been widely used by communities and protest groups when challenging a proposed infrastructural project for their area. This approach may involve citizens establishing new legal precedents or exercising existing legal rights when engaging with a specific project with those rights being used to position a citizen/community in terms of a consent/dissent dichotomy. It is marked by a distinct lack on any participative engagement at the early stages of a policy cycle, indeed in many cases given the lack of engagement by project promoter, it is not so much a case of the last resort, but rather the only resort. In this perspective, public engagement is formalised with the enactment and enhancement of established regulatory mechanisms, with decision-making powers resting with the practitioner of those legal frameworks and not the citizens themselves.

3.3.5 THE PRODUCER – PRODUCTION-BASED PARTICIPATION

Where once the dominant mode of citizen participation was as a consumer¹⁴, recent moves to decarbonise the energy system has facilitated (and in contexts encouraged) citizens to produce energy. This has manifested itself in a number of ways, including: micro-generation ‘prosumption’ of energy, as discussed in Section 3.1.2; banding together with other citizens to form energy production

¹⁴ Indeed, for many traditional energy actors the only legitimate mode of participation was as a consumer

co-operatives¹⁵ (Pietkiewicz, 2016); investing in energy production projects¹⁶; becoming shareholders in energy companies. Indeed this mode of participation has been mainstreamed to the extent that there is often a conflation of energy citizen participation with the very idea of community energy (energy co-operatives or otherwise).

While involving citizens in energy production, in whatever shape that may take, is a very positive development, there are some negatives in an over-emphasis on this form of participation. The promotion of production-based participation invites citizen-consumers to join the club of energy producers, but this is generally only open for those who have sufficient economic and social privilege to do so. Additionally, prospective participation is often channelled towards existing modes of development and more disruptive approaches are (albeit not necessarily explicitly) discouraged or at least not actively facilitated or encouraged¹⁷.

In many respects a focus on production-based participation suits those who favour minimal changes to the status quo. Coupled with the shifting of responsibilities inherent in the 'good citizen' concept (outlined in section 3.3.3), promotion of prosumption (or at least the idea of it) takes the onus away from the energy industry to increase the pace of their decarbonisation, and places the responsibility on making our energy system more suitable back to citizens.

3.3.6 THE CHALLENGER – POLITICS-BASED PARTICIPATION

At its most straight-forward politics-based participation involves citizens working to shape and influence the energy system through engaging in public debate, arguing and organising in support of different perspectives in national and European public arenas. This typically involves challenging the status quo or perceived wisdom. Such participants are often strongly motivated, by a diverse range of local and global issues, including for example: opposition to wind farms (Cass & Walker, 2009); call for increased renewables (Hager, 2015); concern about climate change (Bowman, 2019); anger over energy prices, *etc.* This participation can take many forms depending on circumstance and issue. It can range from formal participation in the decision making process¹⁸, to social movements such as local

¹⁵ Microgeneration can also be realised in small collectives, at this level it can be thought of as representing both collective prosumption while also falling into the cooperative category

¹⁶ This can take a number of forms including *e.g.*, promoters are themselves embedded in community; investment mechanism established as part of project community outreach; local land owners providing sites for renewable energy projects, *etc.*(Lennon et al., 2019)

¹⁷ Mourik et al., (2020, p. 7) for instance observe that 'Community owned energy generation is almost non-existent in Ireland. Administrative, regulatory and financing impediments facing developments are often used to explain such a low take-up – for instance the development process of Ireland's first community owned wind farm in Templederry, Co. Tipperary ha took over twelve years

¹⁸ In line with Mullally *et al.*'s (2018, p. 75) identification of a deliberative discourse '*emphasising a constructive role for energy citizens actively shaping the energy system*'

action group protesting a wind energy development¹⁹. Indeed, many citizens who engage with energy issues will move along this spectrum of activity depending on the circumstances and experiences of those involved.

However, as Barry (2019) argues, very often in a democracy ‘contestation is more important than consensus’ and that it is from such contestation, debate and argument that compromises and agreed ways forward can be found. It is this approach that can be most challenging to the status quo. While governments, regulators and even some energy companies may talk about increasing citizen participation in the energy system, they typically mean a form of bounded decision-making, in which the actual elements on which decisions are to be made are quite limited. The approach favoured by Barry on the other hand could be used to contest the very basis of the decision-making, and in doing so open up the range of decisions to be made, potentially disrupting existing energy configurations and offering the possibility of substantial social innovation.

4 Summary and future work

4.1 Summation

This deliverable aimed to develop an appreciation and understanding of citizen participation and in particular the different modes of participation emerging around energy. We looked first at civic participation in a general sense, considering public participation in the context of the modern state, and exploring a number of prominent modes of citizen participation, including active consumerism, prosumerism, communitarianism and participatory citizenship. Next, a number of (inter-related) concepts central to understanding citizen participation around energy were introduced and briefly discussed, namely: energy justice, energy democracy and energy citizenship²⁰. We saw how the concept of the energy citizen remains a contested idea, with some commentators emphasising a normative perspective focused on responsibilities and obligations of ‘good citizens’, while others placing a greater prominence on rights, arguing for a more inclusive and participatory conceptualisation. Following the contextual review described above and informed by some of our related work (e.g., Dunphy, Revez, Gaffney, Lennon, Sanvicente, et al., 2017; Lennon et al., 2020, 2019; Mullally et al., 2018), we explored examples in the literature of existing and emerging modes of citizen participation within the energy domain. In doing so we identified and described a number of roles that citizens are permitted to play and/or want to play within the energy system, as presented in Box 2.

¹⁹ Lennon *et al.*, (2019, p. 3) observe ‘*While such opposition is often attributed to NIMBYism through oversimplified and perhaps lazy analyses the reality is usually more complicated*’

²⁰ Although the term ‘Energy Citizenship’ has increasing currency in the discourse around the energy transition. However, the concept remains under-theorised, and what form(s) of participation it actually involves in practice remains open to interpretation (Lennon *et al.*, 2020).

- the **passive consumer**, the traditional passive receiver of energy;
- the **active consumer**, encouraged to use their purchasing power to influence the market in certain directions;
- the **good citizen**, who just needs to be informed and they will do the 'right thing';
- The **constitutionalist**, for whom everything is about understanding and enforcing their legal rights;
- The **producer**, who either individually or collectively with others is involved in the production of energy;
- The **challenger**, who engages in public debate, organises and protests to promote alternative perspectives on energy and the energy system.

Box 2: Examples of citizen-consumer roles within the energy system

Of course citizens have overlapping identities, and it is not only possible, but likely that individual citizen-consumers will play different roles within the energy system depending on the circumstance, and perhaps even do so concurrently. For this reason, it is useful perhaps to consider these roles not as strictly demarcated categories, but rather as particular expressions of energy citizenship²¹ deployed at a particular time.

4.2 Next steps

The discussion presented in this report, on citizen-consumer participation, is the first output of a work package focused on mapping participation within the energy system. The developed understandings, descriptions and definitions prepare the ground for the realisation of the principal outputs from this package of work. This will comprise:

- Building on this report and informed by an online survey, an analysis will be conducted of emerging governance and organisational frameworks which act to condition and structure citizen participation in the energy system;
- Combining the work presented in this report with governance and organisation framework analysis, a typology of citizen participation in the energy system will be forwarded. This will capture the relationships between the socio-demographic characteristics of citizens, the cultural narratives around energy to which they adhere, and their participation in the energy system.

²¹ Here the term 'energy citizenship' is used in its most basic understanding *i.e.*, the means by which a citizen-consumer chooses to engage with the energy system.

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